

IMPROVING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LISTENING SKILL

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Abstract: *This article highlights some innovative strategies for improving listening skill of English Language of secondary level students. Effective Listening in English language, guiding the students towards effective oral communication, is the problem with all the ESL students at secondary level and as such it creates problem for English language teachers. The objective of the study was to help the English language teachers and students to overcome this problem by showing the results of application of innovative strategies for improving English language listening skill.*

Keywords: *innovative strategies, listening comprehension, temptation, language listening skill, challenges, frustrate.*

METHODOLOGY

Firstly, translating creates a barrier between the listener and the speaker. Second, most people repeat themselves constantly. By remaining calm, you can usually understand what the speaker had said. Translating Creates a Barrier Between Yourself and the Person Who Is Speaking While you are listening to another person speaking a foreign language, the temptation is to immediately translate into your native language. This temptation becomes much stronger when you hear a word you don't understand. This is only natural as we want to understand everything that is said. However, when you translate into your native language, you are taking the focus of your attention away from the speaker and concentrating on the translation process taking place in your brain. This would be fine if you could put the speaker on hold. In real life, however, the person continues talking while you translate.

RESULTS

This situation obviously leads to less – not more -- understanding. Translation leads to a mental block in your brain, which sometimes doesn't allow you to understand anything at all. Think for a moment about your friends, family, and colleagues. When they speak in your native tongue, do they repeat themselves? If they are like most people, they probably do.

That means that whenever you listen to someone speaking, it is very likely that they will repeat the information, giving you a second, third or even fourth chance to understand what has been said. By remaining calm, allowing yourself to not understand, and not translating while listening, your brain is free to concentrate on the most important thing: understanding English in English. Probably the greatest advantage of using the Internet to improve your listening skills is that you can choose what you would like to listen to and how many and times you would like to listen to it. By listening to something you enjoy, you are also likely to know a lot more of the vocabulary required. Use keywords or key phrases to help you understand the general ideas. If you understand "New York", "business trip", "last year" you can assume that the person is speaking about a business trip to New York last year. This may seem obvious to you, but remember person continues to speak. Let's imagine that your English speaking friend says, "I bought this great tuner at JR's. It was really cheap and now I can finally listen to National Public Radio broadcasts." You don't understand what a tuner is, and if you focus on the word tuner you might become frustrated. If you think in context, you probably will begin to understand. For example; bought is the past of buy, listen is no problem and radio is obvious. Now you understand: He bought something -- the tuner -- to listen to the radio. A tuner must be a kind of radio. This is a simple example but it demonstrates what you need to focus on: Not the word that you don't understand, but the words you do understand.

DISCUSSION

Listening often is the most important way to improve your listening skills. Enjoy the listening possibilities offered by the Internet and remember to relax. Despite its obvious importance to language learning, the listening skill was for a long time relegated to a marginal place in foreign language curricula. With the advent of communicative language teaching and the focus on proficiency, the learning and teaching of listening started to receive more attention. However, listening is not yet fully integrated into the curriculum and needs to be given more "prime time" in class and homework. For learners, listening presents a challenge for a variety of reasons, among which are the following:

- Listening involves multiple modes: Listening involves the interpersonal and interpretive modes of communication. It requires the listener to assume either a participative role in face-to-face conversations, or a non-participative role in listening to other people speak or present.

- Listening involves all varieties of language: In addition to listening to lectures and presentations in academic and formal settings, learners have also to partake or listen to exchanges that involve various levels of colloquialism.

- Listening involves "altered" and "reduced" language forms: In addition to dealing with the vocabulary and structures of the language, listeners have to learn to comprehend reduced forms of the language (e.g., I wanna go, Just a sec).

- Listening involves variable rates of delivery

CONCLUSION

Unlike a reading text that is at the learner's control, a listening text is constantly moving and at variable speeds that often cannot be controlled by the listener, because of all these factors, listening activities often create high levels of anxiety and stress among learners that can interfere with comprehension. For teachers as well, addressing listening in the language classroom poses some challenges. As a language teacher, one of your tasks will be to develop a vision of where listening fits within your teaching. As you progress through this module, continue to think of how you might plan to approach listening activities and what goals and expectations to set for your students.

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